

Mass Spectral Studies of 3-(*p*-fluoro)-benzoylhydrazone-2-indolinones

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Manuscript received 16 March 1982, accepted 10 December 1982

The mass spectra of three 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazone-5-chloro-1-morpholinomethyl-2-indolinones (I-III) have been analysed. It has been observed that I-III undergo McLafferty rearrangement as a primary pathway. Mass spectrum of 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazone-5-chloro-1-methyl-2-indolinone (IV), a closely reported analogue, is also reported.

It has been reported¹ that indol-2,3-dione loses CO, HCN and CO from the molecular ion. Consecutive loss of two molecules of CO from molecular ion followed by HCN occurs as a minor pathway. 1-Methyl-indol-2,3-dione² shows no loss of HCN, instead it eliminates two moles of CO from the molecular ion. The fragmentation pattern of 3-arylimino-2-indolinones³ reveals that the intense molecular ion loses CO and HCN in a competitive manner followed by further fragmentation. Furthermore, 1-methyl-3-arylimino-2-indolinone shows the loss of CHO through an *ortho* effect⁴ involving 2-CO and N-Me function.

In the present paper the mass spectral studies of 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazone-5-chloro-2-indolinones (I-IV) are described. The studies have led to the conclusion that these compounds could be easily characterised by mass spectrometry (Table 1).

I, (R = Cl; X = O)
II, (R = Br; X = O)
III, (R = CH₃; X = CH₂)

IV

The mass spectrum of 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazone-5-chloro-1-morpholinomethyl-2-indolinone (I) exhibited an intense molecular ion peak (1) at *m/e* 416/418 with a characteristic chlorine isotopic pattern. The molecular ion peak then undergoes McLafferty rearrangement (Scheme A), yielding peak 2 at *m/e* 317/319 and a neutral fragment. The fission of 2 leads to base peak (4) at *m/e* 194/196

TABLE I—MASS SPECTRAL FRAGMENTATION OF I-IV
Compound

	I	II	III	IV
1	M ⁺ 416/418	M ⁺ 460/462	M ⁺ 394	M ⁺ 381/383
2	317/319	361/363	297	208/210
3	123	123	123	180/182
4	194/196	238/240	174	152/154
5	166/168	210/212	146	117
6	138/140	182/184	118	75
7	137/139	181/183	117	123
8	102	102	—	95
9	101	101	—	76
10	95	95	95	124
11	76	76	76	303/305
12	289/291	333/335	269	180/182
13	124	124	124	—
14	100	100	98	—
15	70	70	—	—
16	72	72	—	—

Scheme A

and a peak (3) at m/e 123 which could also be obtained from **13** (m/e 124) by the loss of H radical. The ion at m/e 124 is generated from the ion **2** as an alternate pathway. Further fragmentation of **3** leads to ion at m/e 95 (**10**) and m/e 76 (**11**). Loss of a nitrogen molecule from **4** leads to ion **5** at m/e 166/168 which is stabilized by resonance. The ion peak at m/e 289/291 (**12**), resulting by the removal of N_2 from **2** could also give rise to **5**. Further fragments at m/e 138/140, 137/139, 102 and 101 are generated in a stepwise manner when **5** undergoes further fragmentations. The ion **14** (m/e 100) is obtained from **1** from which ions at m/e 70 (**15**) and m/e 72 (**16**) are formed.

The mass spectrum of **II** having bromine atom in place of chlorine (in **I**) confirmed the fragmentation pattern depicted for **I**. The molecular ion peak at m/e 460/462 yields ion **2** at m/e 361/363 and a neutral fragment (M.W. 99) through McLafferty rearrangement. The other fragments derived from **2** are observed at m/e 238/240, 210/212, 182/184, 181/183, 102 and 101 (Scheme B). Fragment **12** appears at m/e 333/335 as a peak of moderate intensity. Other fragments arising from morpholinomethyl or 4-fluorobenzoylhydrazone moiety appear at the same m/e values as in **I**.

Scheme B

The mass spectrum of **III** (M^+ , m/e 394) provided additional evidence for the fragmentation behaviour of such compounds (Scheme C). The

Scheme C

major fragments emanating from M^+ are observed at m/e 297, 174, 146, 118 and 117. The appearance of ion **12** occurs at m/e 269.

The mass spectrum (Scheme D) of 3-(*p*-fluoro)-benzoylhydrazone-5-chloro-1-methyl-2-indolinone (**IV**) has also been examined. The molecular ion is observed at 331/333 as an abundant ion with

Scheme D

chlorine profile. From the M^+ two modes of fragmentations emerge. In one process the M^+ yields ion **7**, which is the base peak. **7** could also arise from **10** by the removal of a hydrogen radical. Loss

of CO and F from 7 in a stepwise manner leads to ions at m/e 95 (8) and m/e 76 (9). The other mode of fragmentation leads to ion 2 (m/e 208/210), 3 (m/e 180/182), 4 (m/e 152/154) and 5 (m/e 117). The ion 11 at m/e 303/305 is generated from M^+ by the loss of CO and ion 12 at m/e 180/182 is obtained from 11.

Experimental⁵

Compounds I-III were obtained by the Mannich condensation with morpholine/piperidine on 3-(*p*-fluoro)benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinones. IV was prepared from 1-methyl-5-chloro-indol-2,3-dione and

4-fluorobenzoic acid hydrazide. The compounds were characterised by correct elemental analysis and ir spectral data.

References

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